

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION		STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT		Cuba Project
				Min: 62.324	Max: 62.664	1419	<input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1950-2		Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 302	
DEFINITION wall east of SU 1424				Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:		
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition					
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are						SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%		
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
						Compaction	Color	
						<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)								
Northern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit			<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Western Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Eastern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE								
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):				
Is abutted by:				Abuts: 1390, 1440				
Is covered by: 1327				Covers: 1001				
Is cut by:				Cuts:				
Is filled by:				Fills:				
OBSERVATIONS wall extends east along SU 1424 and connects to SU 1390								
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: south central area B 2011, runs east along 1424 and northern limit abuts wall 1390 Shape: rectangular								
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)								
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):				

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: north → south

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions: —

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) 3-10cm Medium (range) 20-25cm Large (range) 33-51cm Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type —

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

length 225cm height east 18cm
width 54cm height west 12cm

Description:
opus mixtum well
running north to south

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North) SU1390

INTERPRETATION

Well abuts wall SU1390, construction cut 1441 curving at northern limit suggests that 1390 and 1449 were built contemporaneously. Well 1449 tapers off at southern limit, might have continued south.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Z. Fox on 7/26/11

Revised by CAM on 26.7.2011

PDFd by BUR on 27.7.2011

Entered by on